

NONLINEAR VISCOELASTIC CHARACTERIZATION OF FILLED ELASTOMER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Filled elastomers exhibit highly nonlinear viscoelastic behavior as demonstrated by a large dynamic strain amplitude dependence of the dynamic moduli. Dynamic testing has been performed over a range of dynamic amplitudes on a variety of filled elastomers. Also, stress-strain curves were generated from constant strain rate tests at 4 rates, with static offsets. Static offsets have minimal effect on both dynamic and stress-strain curves. Frequency dependence is greatest at the lowest dynamic amplitudes and minimal for high dynamic amplitudes. The ramp and storage moduli closely mirror one another at corresponding strain amplitudes. The normalized moduli of a group of natural rubber/carbon blacks is similar, suggesting that surface area and structure influence the magnitude of the reinforcing mechanism, but not the general behavior. The data suggest that a strain rate activated structural change in the filler is occurring, which is viscously coupled to the elastomeric matrix.

KEYWORDS: filled elastomer, nonlinear viscoelasticity, storage and loss modulus, strain rate, damping

INTRODUCTION

The presence of fillers in elastomers serves to enhance many properties, notably dynamic mechanical behavior. Unfilled elastomers exhibit the classical Gaussian behavior in that they have linear shear stress-strain curves, and have low stiffness and low damping. The filler serves to dramatically increase both stiffness and damping. The dynamic behavior of filled elastomers is highly nonlinear and not well understood.

A number of engineering applications require quantitative damping information for the proper performance of the design. One example is the lead-lag damper of a rotorcraft. This is the damper which provides in-plane damping and is critical to the performance of the helicopter.

EXPERIMENTAL

Payne [1,2] was the first to perform dynamic mechanical characterization on carbon black reinforced vulcanizates by testing samples of cylinders 2.54 cm high by 0.8 cm radius in shear in which the shear plane was parallel to the circular cross-section. This is an imperfect test

geometry since the sample is subject to a highly nonuniform strain field (not uniform shear) and the modulus thus obtained is actually an apparent modulus.

Materials

The dynamic behavior of a number of filled elastomers was measured. Proprietary samples were provided by Lord Corporation, and included natural rubber (NR) reinforced with carbon black at four filler levels, 11 silicone reinforced with silica, and two blends. In addition, Lord Corporation provided a set of natural rubber samples reinforced with one of four different carbon blacks at 15, 45, and 75 phr (parts per hundred rubber). Table 1 shows the four carbon blacks and their respective surface area and structure. There are four combinations of high and low surface area and structure.

Table I: Area and structure of carbon blacks to reinforce natural rubber.

Filler	Area by Iodine	Structure by DBP	Filler Levels
Vulcan 5H	81	150	15, 45, 69
Sterling 5550	82	72	15, 45, 75
Sterling 4620	20	126	15, 45, 75
Sterling NS-1 V-4655	28	64	15, 45, 75

Sample Geometry

The sample geometry is critical to the quality of the data. Elastomers have nonlinear behavior in tension/compression, with rapidly increasing modulus in compression, and decreasing modulus in tension. Simple shear behavior is symmetrical about the undeformed state.

End effects can significantly affect the data if an improper geometry is used. A sample of low aspect ratio (loaded surface to free surface area ratio) will have significant end effects and a dramatically reduced apparent modulus, even at infinitesimal strains [3]. For the testing in this research, a concentric cylinder geometry was used (Fig. 1). The elastomer is bonded to two cylinders, an inner and an outer, resulting in an integrated sample/fixture. The annular geometry has no edges in the circumferential direction and hence an “infinite” aspect ratio. The aspect ratio is 8 in the height to thickness, and radius to thickness is sufficient to minimize end effects and produce a nearly homogeneous strain field [3].

It is particularly important to have a homogeneous strain field when measuring nonlinear material behavior, otherwise the nonlinear material response will be obscured by the nonuniform strain field, making it difficult, if not impossible, to extract the material nonlinear behavior.

An additional feature of the concentric cylinder/annulus geometry is that it enables two orthogonal shears (axial and torsional) to be imposed on the sample, either or both being any combination of static and dynamic shear components.

Fig. 1: Sample geometry used for dynamic testing.

Dynamic Testing

The integrated sample/fixture is mounted to two fixtures which are inserted into collets on an Instron 1321 biaxial (torsion/tension) servohydraulic testing machine.

The Instron is linked to a Dynalyzer (an FFT based dynamic analyzer), which produces a digitally generated reference signal which is transmitted to the controlling channel and receives load and displacement transducer signals from the selected channels. The Dynalyzer performs a Fourier analysis on these signals with respect to the reference signal to determine the phase angle between them. The static components of the load and displacement signals are rejected as well as any harmonics that may be present. The Dynalyzer computes the storage and loss modulus, displacement and force signal amplitudes, and transmits them digitally to a PC. Calibration constants, machine compliance and electronic phase shift corrections are handled in software provided with the Dynalyzer.

The maximum dynamic range is attained by performing a test in dynamic torsion load control. The sizing of the Instron and the load cells is such that the capability of the machine to control in load is much better than in stroke control for very low dynamic amplitudes.

Dynamic moduli are recorded at each frequency in a sweep, where a sweep consists of a fixed dynamic load amplitude, performed at 21 frequencies from 0.1 to 10 Hz, evenly spaced on a log scale. The dynamic amplitude was increased from the lowest to the highest amplitude. The lowest load amplitude was determined from minimal acceptable load resolution. The highest load amplitude was determined from either the maximum possible load at that scale or from the LVDT displacement transducer maximum scale if the sample was soft.

Orthogonal static offset tests were performed on the elastomers by imposing dynamic loading in the torsional mode with static axial displacement. In addition, parallel shear offsets were performed by performing dynamic displacement in torsion with static angular displacement. It is not possible to obtain as low a dynamic amplitude in this manner since displacement control cannot be controlled with good resolution at very small displacements.

Ramp Testing

Stress-strain curves are generated by a constant strain rate test controlled by a computer. Both ramp time and amplitude can be chosen. For this study, ramps were performed up to 5 percent shear strain in 2, 20, 200, and 2000 seconds, corresponding to strain rates from $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ to $2.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ per second.

All samples were ramped to 10 percent shear strain at the nominal rate of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ per second prior to the test ramps. After the initial conditioning ramp, 10 minutes were allowed to elapse before initiating the fastest ramp. After the first ramp, a static offset of 1 percent shear strain was set, and 10 minutes were allowed to elapse before initiating the next ramp. This sequence was repeated up to 5 percent static shear strain. Subsequent ramp tests at lower rates were carried out in the same fashion, always with a 10 minute elapsed time between tests.

RESULTS

Dynamic mechanical testing was performed on all samples. Representative data will be shown to illustrate general features common to most or all of the samples.

Dynamic Results

The dynamic response of the natural rubber/carbon black in Fig. 2 shows the typical qualitative features that all filled elastomers exhibit. The storage modulus is highest at the smallest dynamic amplitudes and monotonically decreases to some limiting value at high dynamic amplitudes. The loss modulus curves show the typical loss peak which occurs at approximately the same dynamic amplitude range where the storage modulus is most rapidly decreasing.

To more clearly show that this behavior is typical of filled elastomers, the storage and loss modulus of a silicone filled with silica is shown in Fig. 3.

As stated above, the storage and loss modulus show qualitatively the same behavior as the natural rubber/carbon black, albeit with different magnitudes. The silicone/silica sample appears to have an asymmetrical loss peak whereas the NR/carbon black has a symmetrical loss peak. In addition, the ratio of the low amplitude modulus to the modulus at high amplitude reaches 16 to 1 (at 0.1 Hz) for the silicone rubber sample.

Another feature common to both systems is that the frequency dependence is greatest at the smallest dynamic amplitudes. For both systems, as the dynamic amplitude increases, the three curves shown (0.1, 1.0, and 10 Hz) converge. This is particularly so for the storage modulus, but also is apparent in the loss behavior as well.

The effect of static offset, either parallel or orthogonal, is important to the understanding of the behavior of elastomers under dynamic conditions. For both the storage and loss moduli, the effect of static offset is to reduce the moduli somewhat, but it is far less than the effect of dynamic amplitude, and can be considered a second order effect. Fig. 4 shows the effect of a parallel static offset on the storage and loss modulus of a NR/carbon black at dynamic amplitude of 0.025. Similarly, the effect of an orthogonal static offset on the dynamic moduli is small.

Payne constructed a plot of the loss peak versus the change in storage modulus for a number of natural rubbers filled with carbon black [1]. This same plot has been constructed for all of the data on NR/carbon blacks and silicone/silica samples for this research and is shown in Fig. 5.

The Payne curve in Fig. 5 does not indicate where a particular elastomer will lie, merely that there is an overall correlation between the loss peak and the storage modulus. To determine where a particular elastomer lies on the Payne curve, a filler effectiveness curve is necessary. Such a curve is shown in Fig. 6 for a series of NR/carbon blacks.

Fig. 2: Storage and loss moduli versus dynamic amplitude for a highly filled natural rubber/carbon black elastomer system.

Fig. 3: Storage and loss modulus of a silicone filled with silica.

The filler effectiveness curve shows the pronounced nonlinear dependence on filler content for all four fillers. The effect of surface area is clearly stronger than that of the structure. The Vulcan 5H and the ST 5550 have nearly the same surface area, but different structures, yet their change in moduli is fairly close. The ST 4620 and the SNS1 V-4655 have low surface areas and different structures and again their behavior is similar.

Harmonic Paradox

If the nonlinear dynamic amplitude dependence is merely a manifestation of a nonlinear stress-strain curve, then the presence of a static offset should have a significant effect on the dynamic moduli. However, the data show that this is not the case. In addition, the harmonics of the response are 25 to 35 decibels below the fundamental, indicating that the response is in fact, “linear.” This presents a “harmonic paradox,” in which the material exhibits pronounced nonlinear amplitude dependence, yet has a “linear” response to the sinusoidal excitation. This suggests that a series of stress-strain curves at various static offsets would be illuminating.

Fig. 4: Effect of parallel static offset on the dynamic moduli of an NR/carbon black filled elastomer.

Stress-Strain Results

The stress-strain response with static offsets of a natural rubber filled with carbon black (Vulcan 5H, 69 phr) is shown in Fig. 7.

The effect of a static offset on the stress-strain response is negligible. The material responds as if there were no offset. The initial modulus of a nonlinear elastic material would be a function of the total strain level, and would therefore be dependent on the static strain level.

The instantaneous modulus of the elastomers in the constant strain rate test further illuminates their dynamic response. As seen in Fig. 8, there is considerable agreement between the storage modulus and the ramp modulus at a fixed nominal rate for a highly filled natural rubber with carbon black. It is important to note that for dynamic results, the strain rate is not

constant and is an “average” of rates from 0 to some maximum, and that on the next half-cycle varies from 0 to the negative of the maximum value. In addition, the nominal slewing rate of the dynamic test varies proportionately with dynamic amplitude. Despite these differences, the similarities in the two curves is striking.

Fig. 5: Loss peak versus change in storage modulus for Payne[1] and present work.

Fig. 6: Filler effectiveness curves for carbon blacks in NR. Legend: HA, high area; LA, low area; HS, high structure; LS, low structure.

DISCUSSION

All of the elastomers tested (30 in all) show qualitatively the same phenomena. They show the storage modulus at low dynamic amplitude decreasing markedly with increasing dynamic amplitude. The loss peak occurs at approximately the same dynamic amplitude range in which the marked change in storage modulus occurs.

The extent of the change in the storage modulus and the strength of the loss peak are clearly related to the filler level. The changes in the dynamic moduli increase nonlinearly with filler content, with the most rapid increase occurring in the high filler content range.

The presence of a static offset, either parallel or orthogonal, has a minimal second order effect on the dynamic moduli. The effect that is seen is most pronounced for the storage modulus at low dynamic amplitudes, and near the peak for the loss modulus. Since a static offset does not alter significantly the dynamic response, it appears that it cannot be due to merely a nonlinear stress-strain response. This observation led to a critical experiment in which the stress-strain response and the effect of static offsets on that response were tested.

The stress-strain response of filled elastomers show a marked nonlinearity with a high modulus at the outset, and a terminal modulus which is significantly lower. The initial modulus is highly strain rate dependent, whereas the terminal modulus is nearly strain rate independent (Fig. 9). This mirrors the frequency dependence which is greatest at low dynamic amplitudes and minimal at high dynamic amplitudes.

Fig. 7: Stress-strain curves for NR/carbon black with static offsets.

Fig. 8: Comparison of storage modulus, G' (at 1 Hz) and ramp modulus at nominal strain rate of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ per second.

Fig. 9: Initial and terminal modulus from a stress-strain curve taken at $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ per second strain rate.

The ramp modulus can be normalized so that its value is 1 at its maximum and 0 at its minimum, according to Eqn 1.

$$G_{\text{norm}} = \frac{G - G_{\text{min}}}{G_{\text{max}} - G_{\text{min}}} \quad (1)$$

This normalized modulus is then a measure of the proportion of modulus change remaining. A plot of normalized modulus versus strain amplitude is seen in Fig. 10. Despite the large differences in filler systems, the normalized moduli show remarkable agreement. The specific filler used in an elastomer will dramatically affect the magnitude of the response but not the general behavior of it.

Fig. 10: Normalized modulus versus strain amplitude for the series of carbon blacks (highly filled).

These results suggest that a strain rate activated structural change of filler is occurring and that it is viscously coupled to the matrix. There is a material state that is determined by strain rate and is the result of an equilibrium between breakdown and reformation processes. In the case of dynamic tests, some “average” strain rate controls the steady-state structure or material state. The ramp tests indicate that the material rapidly equilibrates to the current strain rate, independent of the static strain level.

CONCLUSIONS

Dynamic testing has been performed over a 3 decade range of dynamic amplitudes on a variety of filled elastomers. Stress-strain curves were generated from constant strain rate tests covering 3 decades. Static offsets were found to have minimal effect on both dynamic and stress-strain behavior. The ramp and storage moduli closely mirror one another at corresponding strain amplitudes. The data suggest that a strain rate activated structural change in the filler is occurring, and is viscously coupled to the elastomeric matrix. The results cannot be explained by a nonlinear elastic network theory.

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